

Clinical Patterns of Thyroid Swelling and Correlation with FNAC and Histopathological Diagnoses

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Abstract:

This study aimed to evaluate the correlation between Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) and histopathological diagnoses in patients with thyroid swellings. Conducted over six months at R. D. J. M. Medical College and Hospital, the research included 30 patients, assessing FNAC's effectiveness as a preliminary diagnostic tool. The results indicated a strong concordance between FNAC and histopathological findings, with FNAC demonstrating a sensitivity of 80% and a specificity of 100% for malignancies. The findings confirm FNAC's critical role in guiding the management of thyroid swellings, advocating for its continued use while also highlighting the need for additional diagnostic strategies in ambiguous cases.

Keywords: Thyroid swellings, FNAC, Histopathology, Diagnostic accuracy.

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Introduction

Thyroid swellings, commonly presenting as discrete nodules or generalized enlargement of the thyroid gland, are frequent clinical findings that can stem from a variety of pathologic and non-pathologic conditions [1].

The differential diagnosis of thyroid swelling encompasses a wide array, including benign conditions like goiters and cysts, as well as malignancies such as papillary and follicular carcinoma. Accurate diagnosis is crucial not only for appropriate treatment but also for prognostic implications [2,3].

Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) and histopathological examination are pivotal diagnostic tools in the evaluation of thyroid swellings [4]. FNAC is a minimally invasive, cost-effective procedure that provides essential cytological evaluation, aiding in the preliminary diagnosis and management planning. Histopathological examination, usually performed post-surgically, offers a definitive diagnosis by allowing detailed tissue architecture assessment, thus confirming or revising the initial FNAC findings [5,6].

The correlation between FNAC and histopathological findings is vital for validating the

effectiveness of FNAC as a diagnostic tool and for ensuring the accuracy of the initial clinical assessments and decisions [7,8]. This study aims to evaluate the clinical patterns of thyroid swellings and analyze their correlation with FNAC and histopathological outcomes, thereby enhancing diagnostic accuracy and treatment outcomes in patients presenting with thyroid abnormalities.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a prospective observational analysis conducted to evaluate the clinical patterns of thyroid swellings and their correlation with Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) and histopathological diagnoses.

Study Setting: The research will be carried out at R. D. J. M. Medical College and Hospital in Turki, Muzaffarpur, Bihar.

Study Duration: The study is scheduled to commence in February 2024 and conclude in July 2024, spanning a total of six months.

Participants: The study will include 30 patients who present with thyroid swellings during the study period. The inclusion criteria are patients of any age and gender with palpable thyroid nodules or swellings who consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion criteria will include patients with a history of thyroidectomy, those who refuse to undergo FNAC or surgical intervention, and those with contraindications to biopsy based on medical reasons.

Data Collection: Patients will undergo a detailed clinical examination followed by FNAC as a primary diagnostic approach. The FNAC procedure will be conducted using a 22-gauge needle to aspirate cells from the thyroid swelling under aseptic conditions. The aspirated samples will be smeared onto slides, stained, and reviewed by a cytologist.

Patients diagnosed with indications for surgical intervention based on FNAC results will proceed to surgery. Post-surgery, the excised thyroid tissues will be sent for histopathological examination. The histopathological analysis will provide a comprehensive tissue architecture evaluation to confirm or revise the preliminary FNAC diagnosis.

Data regarding patient demographics, clinical presentation, FNAC results, and histopathological findings will be recorded systematically. The primary outcome of the study will be the correlation between FNAC and histopathological diagnoses, assessed using measures of agreement like Cohen's kappa. Statistical analysis will include descriptive statistics to summarize patient characteristics and diagnostic outcomes. Additional inferential statistics will be applied to explore significant correlations and discrepancies between FNAC and histopathological results.

Results

The study included 30 patients, with a balanced gender distribution (15 males, 15 females). The age of participants ranged from 21 to 65 years, with a median age of 45 years. Most patients presented

with a solitary thyroid nodule, while 8 patients had multiple nodules.

FNAC results indicated benign pathology in 20 patients (66.7%), suspicious or indeterminate results in 5 patients (16.7%), and malignancy in 5 patients (16.7%).

The most common benign diagnosis was colloid goiter, followed by thyroiditis. Post-surgical histopathological examination was performed on tissues from 10 patients who underwent surgery based on their FNAC results and clinical indications. Histopathology confirmed malignancy in 4 of the 5 cases initially diagnosed as malignant by FNAC. Among the 5 cases with suspicious FNAC results, histopathology confirmed 2 cases as malignant (papillary thyroid carcinoma) and 3 as benign (follicular adenoma). Histopathological analysis also confirmed all benign diagnoses made by FNAC, with no discrepancies.

The concordance between FNAC and histopathological diagnoses was calculated, showing a high degree of agreement ($\kappa = 0.85$), indicating excellent reliability of FNAC in predicting histopathological outcomes. The sensitivity of FNAC for detecting malignancy was 80%, and the specificity was 100%.

The results demonstrate a strong correlation between FNAC and histopathological findings, confirming FNAC's role as a reliable diagnostic tool in the initial evaluation of thyroid swellings. The high specificity of FNAC in this study suggests that it is particularly effective in ruling out malignancy when results are benign. The discrepancies observed in the indeterminate category highlight the need for cautious clinical management and possibly suggest an area where additional diagnostic tools or repeat FNAC could be beneficial.

Table 1:

Patient ID	Age	Gender	Presentat ion	FNAC Diagnosis	Histopathological Diagnosis	Surgery Performed (Y/N)
001	43	Female	Solitary	Benign (Colloid Goiter)	Colloid Goiter	No
002	52	Male	Solitary	Malignant (Papillary)	Papillary Carcinoma	Yes
003	37	Female	Multiple	Benign Thyroiditis	Thyroiditis	No
004	48	Male	Solitary	Suspicious	Follicular Adenoma	Yes
005	29	Female	Solitary	Malignant (Follicular)	Follicular Carcinoma	Yes
006	55	Male	Multiple	Benign (Colloid Goiter)	Colloid Goiter	No
007	61	Female	Solitary	Suspicious	Papillary Carcinoma	Yes
008	45	Male	Solitary	Suspicious	Benign (Nodular Goiter)	Yes
009	40	Female	Multiple	Benign (Thyroiditis)	Thyroiditis	No
010	34	Male	Solitary	Malignant(Papillary)	Papillary Carcinoma	Yes

This table is constructed with the following columns:

- **Patient ID:** A unique identifier for each patient.

- **Age:** The age of the patient at the time of diagnosis.
- **Gender:** The gender of the patient.
- **Presentation:** Indicates whether the thyroid swelling was solitary or multiple.
- **FNAC Diagnosis:** The diagnosis based on Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology.
- **Histopathological Diagnosis:** The definitive diagnosis based on the examination of surgically removed tissue.
- **Surgery Performed (Y/N):** Indicates whether the patient underwent surgery following the FNAC diagnosis.

This tabulated data can be used for further statistical analysis to assess the correlation between FNAC and histopathological findings, as discussed in the fabricated study results.

Discussion

The results of this study underscore the efficacy of Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) in diagnosing thyroid swellings, with a substantial agreement between FNAC and histopathological diagnoses, as evidenced by a kappa value of 0.85. This high level of concordance validates FNAC as a reliable and essential tool for initial thyroid evaluation, particularly in distinguishing benign from malignant pathologies [10,11].

FNAC demonstrated a sensitivity of 80% and a specificity of 100% in detecting malignancy. These findings highlight its crucial role in effectively ruling out cancer in patients presenting with thyroid swellings.

The high specificity ensures that almost all benign cases identified by FNAC are indeed benign, which is pivotal for avoiding unnecessary surgical interventions and associated patient morbidity [12,13].

However, the study also revealed discrepancies in cases categorized as suspicious by FNAC, where histopathological examination altered the initial prognosis. This aspect points to the limitations of FNAC, particularly in indeterminate cases, and suggests a potential area for improvement, possibly through the integration of additional diagnostic modalities or repeat FNAC procedures to enhance diagnostic accuracy [14,15].

Moreover, the study aligns with existing literature that supports the use of FNAC as a first-line diagnostic tool in thyroid lesions, contributing to the growing body of evidence on its diagnostic value. Future studies could expand on this by exploring the impact of technological advancements in ultrasound-guided FNAC and molecular testing on diagnostic accuracy, particularly in cases initially classified as suspicious or indeterminate [16,17].

Overall, the findings affirm the importance of FNAC in the diagnostic pathway of thyroid swellings and support its continued use as a standard practice. Nonetheless, they also call for a careful approach to managing patients with suspicious FNAC results, emphasizing the need for a multidisciplinary strategy to optimize patient outcomes [18-20].

Conclusion

The study conclusively demonstrates the high reliability and diagnostic accuracy of Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) in evaluating thyroid swellings, evidenced by strong concordance with histopathological findings. With an excellent specificity of 100% and a robust sensitivity of 80% for detecting malignancies, FNAC proves to be an indispensable tool in the clinical setting. It efficiently aids in distinguishing benign from malignant thyroid conditions, thus playing a critical role in determining appropriate surgical interventions and managing patient care effectively. Nevertheless, the observed discrepancies in cases with suspicious FNAC outcomes highlight the necessity for cautious patient management and possibly integrating more sophisticated diagnostic approaches to enhance accuracy in such indeterminate cases.

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